

ISic3013

Statue of Demeter with inscribed base

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication; list of
magistrates

Material

limestone

Object

statue

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2011.04.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Borgellusa di Avola

Provenance

contrada Bargalluzzo (Borgellusa di Avola) , Oct. 1954, chance find

Coordinates

36.918320,

15.156483

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 54224

Physical Description

A limestone statue of Demeter, holding a large torch in right hand and a piglet in her left. The rear of the stone is cut straight and the

statue is in full

relief rather than free-standing, with the stone left intact

below to form a

pedastal.

Dimensions

Height 62 cm

Width 30.3 cm

Depth 17 cm

Layout

The text is engraved over six lines on a flat field 30.3 cm wide and 12-13 cm

high. The left and right sides of this field are cut smooth,

the upper and lower

edges are uneven. The lower right and left corners are

slightly damaged. The

inscription is intact apart from damage to the middle of

line 1 where the upper

front edge of the plinth has been damaged. There is a

clear vacat to the bottom

and right of the text. The first line is larger and extends

to left and right of

the rest of the text. Lines 2-6 have a consistent left

margin.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Alpha has broken bar; epsilon and sigma are lunate; omega is lightly but clearly

rhomboid; omicron is smaller than the other letters and sits above the line; phi is extended well above and below the line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 8-13 mm

Interlineation

Line line1 to line1 : ? mm

Lines 2-6: 5-9 mm

Text

1. προστά τ [αι] Δ,ά,μ,α,τρος
2. Γάϊος Ὀρκήιος Γαίου
3. Γάϊος Σολπίκιος Γαίου
4. Λεύκιος Καύλιος Λευκίου
5. Χαιρήτιος Χαιρητίου
6. Λύκων Νύμφωνος

Apparatus

Translation (en)

The 'prostatai' of Demeter: Gaios Orkeios, son of Gaios; Gaios Solpikios, son of Gaios; Leukios

Kaulios, son of Leukios; Chairetios son of Chairetios; Lykon son of Nymphon

Commentary

The statue is one of three found together close to the coast at Contrada Borgelusa di Avola, in the immediate vicinity of the site of a first-century BC Roman villa (which had an earlier Hellenistic building underneath). The other two statues are Kore and a youthful Herakles. Demeter holds a huge torch in her right hand and piglet in left. The inscription lists five prostatai (guardians of the shrine) of Damater (Demeter). The first three names are Latin / Roman: Gaius Orceius, Gaius Sulpicius, and Lucius Caulius. Gentili (1954) records the discovery; a Roman villa was subsequently excavated in the immediate vicinity. Manganaro (2009) is the most recent discussion, dating the statue to the second century BC.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645361

EDCS 71000788

PHI 331248

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0981

Gentili, G.V. 1954. 2792. Avola. Ritrovamenti vari.. *Fasti Archaeologici*. 9: 204 no.2792.

Manganaro, G. 1977. Per la storia dei culti nella Sicilia greca. *Cronache di Archeologia*. 16: 148-164. At 159 ph

Bacci, G. M. 1984-1985. Avola (1980-1983) - Villa ellenistico-romana in contrada Borgellusa. *Kokalos*. 30-31: 711-713. At 713

Manganaro, G. 2009. Divinità femminili nell'area peloritana e siracusana e l'emergenza di italici nella sicilia tardo ellenistica. *Sicilia Antiqua*. 6: 111-116. At 114 ph

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3013. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357078>

Photo J. Prag